

Original Research Report

Purpose-Based Career Coaching as a Strategy for Increasing Employability of Graduates: A Survey Study

Mkpoikanke Sunday Otu^{1*}

¹Department of Educational Psychology, University of Johannesburg, 2006, Johannesburg, South Africa.

²Department of Educational Foundations, University of Nigeria, 410001, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria.

³Department of Guidance & Counselling, Universitas Negeri Padang, Jalan. Prof. Dr. Hamka Air Tawar Padang 25131, Indonesia.

***Correspondence:** Mkpoikanke Sunday Otu, Department of Educational Psychology, University of Johannesburg, 2006, Johannesburg, South Africa (Email: mkpoikanke.otu@unn.edu.ng).

Abstract: This study investigated teachers' and counsellors' perception of a purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria. The design employed to conduct this study was a cross-sectional survey design that featured desk research and sensitivity workshop. The participants were 100 teachers and 100 counsellors from South-East region of Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in this study. Purpose-based Career Coaching and Employability Questionnaire" (PCCEQ) was used to collect data, while descriptive and inferential analysis were used to analyse data. The results obtained revealed that the knowledge level of the teachers and counsellors increased through the sensitivity workshop with respect to the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates. In addition, with a slight significant difference, the perception of both teachers and the counsellors was high in terms of application, workability and effectiveness of the purpose-based career coaching. Gender did not have any significant contribution or influence on the participants' perceptions. Therefore, the conclusion reached in this study is that teachers and counsellors perceived purpose-based career coaching as effective, applicable and workable strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria.

Keywords: Coaching, Counsellors, Employability, Graduates, Purpose-Based Career Coaching

1. Introduction

There is still a low rate of employability among graduates, and corresponding high rate of unemployment, underemployment, low productivity, dissatisfaction, and unfulfilled purpose among young people (Otu & Omeje, 2021). Despite the fact that numerous career theories have been developed and adopted over the past few years to assist young people in choosing and developing a career path, time has revealed that most of these theories do not apply to everyone, and many of them are difficult to apply without the assistance of an expert or practitioner. Moreover, most of the theories generally focus on individuals, the environment and how they interact. There is no single theory that is suitable for all situations or every individual; one type of theory cannot be applied to all types of individuals or environments; one theory may not be applicable over the long run (Zunker, 2011).

Earlier in International history, Parson's vocational counselling paradigm of matching individual traits with requirements of occupations (Parsons, 1909) was a popular way of helping young people in their career choice. In his Trait-and-factor theory, Parson attempted to match the individual's traits with the requirements of a specific occupation, thereby deciphering the career-search puzzle. The trait-and-factor theory evolved from early studies of individual differences and developed closely with the psychometric movement. This theory significantly influenced the study of job descriptions and job requirements as theorist attempted to predict future job success by measuring job-related traits. The distinctive attribute of this theory is the postulation that individuals have unique patterns of ability and/or traits that can be empirically measured and linked with the requirements of various types of jobs.

Likewise, some counsellors and career advisors follow Ann Roe's career theory which states that people choose their career based on their interaction with their parents (Roe, 1953). While being influenced by Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow, 1987), Ann Roe described how we cultivate our attitudes and interest, and how this serves as an indicator of our occupational satisfaction (Roe, 1953). To her, early experiences and interactions with parents and caregivers influence a child's beliefs, attitudes, interests and needs especially as it regards career interest. That is, the degree and nature of affirmation, rebuke, praise, criticism, verbal and non-verbal encouragement, denial of rights, provision of basic needs (food, water, clothing, toys, etc.), inclusion in domestic chores and involvement in decision-making goes a long way in forming the personality of the child, and this helps to shape their career attitudes and interests in life. Also, the nature of interactions with parents/caregivers brings about physiological needs in people through which they try to satisfy in their career. Also, Robert Hoppock composite theory have influenced career choice and development. This theory suggests that the basis of choosing a specific occupation is the belief that it will meet one's needs (Hoppock, 1967). The needs may be imprecisely felt or clearly understood. However, in either case they do influence choice of career. According to Hoppock, vocational development starts with the awareness that a career can meet needs and progresses till they are fulfilled.

Another influential theoretical career position in history is Super's theory of career development (Super, 1957). Super's theory suggests that an individual will choose an occupation that lets him/her function in a specific role that is congruent with his/her self-concept. Furthermore, Super noted that career planning was a constant process and not just a single choice. His work promotes keeping an individual under observation as he makes career progression during his life rather than merely predicting initial occupational entry. A person goes through several occupational stages during his/her life. At each of these life stages, a person is faced with certain occupational tasks, which if successfully completed, will enable him/her to make advancement to the next developmental stage (Super, 1980).

John Holland stated that individuals are attracted to a given career because of their particular personalities and numerous variables that constitute their backgrounds (Holland & Holland, 1977). To Holland, the major determinant factor in career choice is a comparison of self with the perception of an occupation and subsequent acceptance or rejection. Central to Holland's theory is the concept that one chooses a career to satisfy one's preferred modal personal orientation such as R (realistic occupation), I (investigative), A (artistic), S (social), E (enterprising), and C (conventional) (Holland & Holland, 1977). Notwithstanding, Ginzberg, Ginsburg, Axelrad, and Herma, believed that occupational choice progressed through three periods: Fantasy (birth to 11, where Play becomes work oriented); Tentative (11-17, where there is expression of career interest, capacity, value, and transition; Realistic (17 plus, where exploration, crystallization, and specification take place (Ginzberg et al., 1951). Also, Tiedeman and O'Hara belong to a group that believed career development occurs as individual resolved ego-relevant crises (Grande, 1964). They considered career life decisions and career decisions as integrally related.

Furthermore, Krumboltz et al. (1975) postulated that career selection is based on genetic endowments or special abilities, environmental conditions or events, learning experiences and task approach skills. Krumboltz developed happenstance approach theory for career counselling based on the premise that chance events over one's life span can have both positive career consequences if skills like curiosity, persistence, flexibility, optimism, and risk taking—are applied. This simply means that one can find a satisfied career by chance, and by having positive attitudes toward the events of life.

The list of career theories can go on and on, but it is clear the journey so far is not producing enough solutions. Most local peculiarities are not captured by existing theories, and applicability in local settings is difficult or highly dependent on unavailable conditions. Hence, career counsellors, career coaches, and teachers still find it very challenging to assist young people in making the right career choices and undergoing the necessary development processes with the goal to achieve fulfillment in life. It is imperative that career coaching and education rediscover innovative ways to solve these problems. The result may be the development of new careers, the reformulation of operational policies, the redesigning of training curriculums, and the repackaging of career institutions. As a result, careers may need to be re-imagined, spiritualized and refocused through purpose-based career coaching (Pb-CC) to increase employability.

1.1. Theoretical Framework

The purpose-based career coaching (Pb-CC) concept was developed by Mkpoikanke Sunday Otu in 2016 as an approach for career choice and development. The tenet of this concept is that individuals choose a career that falls in the category of their perceived purpose so they can fulfill the purpose. Also, individuals engage in career development processes they believe will enhance the fulfillment of their perceived purpose. Thus, in line with purpose-based career coaching principles, career is seen as a platform for fulfilling purpose, while career development is seen as a preparation for purpose fulfillment. According to the originator, the fundamental beliefs holding this concept are as follows: Each individual has a divine mandate to fulfill his or her purpose. Individuals may easily achieve this when their career aligns with their purpose. A career is created for a specific purpose, just as a man is created for a specific purpose. Thus, it is essential for individuals to align themselves with the purpose of their chosen career and discover why this is important to them. A career's success depends on how well it fulfills its purpose, as well as how well it enables an individual to fulfill his purpose. A purpose-based career is a divine strategy for meeting needs and solving problems. As a result of purpose-based

careers, God empowers people to address society's needs and solve problems. Purpose-based careers transform people and society. In order to achieve national and personal transformations, every career should be viewed as a means of change. It is possible to enforce righteousness, peace, and justice in society through one's career if it is purpose-driven. In spite of man's effort to achieve what he wants, 'the Creator's (God) will' surpasses all. Consequently, walking in submission to God's will is a good thing that is possible through a purpose-based career. Investing in a career that corresponds with God's will, plan, and purpose is crucial. An individual's career consumes more than 70% of their lifetime - encompassing schooling, training, preparation, working, and professionalization. One may not have tangible time to fulfill one's purpose in a lifetime if the career does not relate to one's life purpose. The affairs of man are important to God. So, every aspect of a man's career should be approached with a godly perspective. Every career is important as long as it meets the needs of society or solves human problems. Money-driven careers and careers driven by prestige will not often succeed. It is said that money is the root of all evil, and that some have wandered from their purpose as a result of their longing for money. Through the help of purpose-based career coaches or counsellors, people can seek direction from God in their careers.

Several workshops and conferences have been conducted to share the concept and techniques of purpose-based career coaching to students, parents, teachers, researchers, counsellors and other career stakeholders. A few of such workshops and conferences are highlighted below: Counselling Summit with the theme; "Reimagining your career for a global fit": The summit was held at the University of Nigeria Nsukka on 12th December 2022, with more than 120 undergraduate and early graduate students as well as teachers, counsellors, and lecturer participants. Highlights of the discussion include career thought process, imagination, purpose, and prospects. Also, purpose-based career coaching was presented to the international community at the 4th Progress in Social Science, Humanities and Education Research Symposium organised by Universitas Negeri Padang, Indonesia, and others.

1.2. Conceptual Analysis

Harvey (2010) defined employability as the ability of a graduate to get a satisfying job. However, it should be noted that what truly gives one satisfaction is the fulfillment of one's purpose. This therefore means that if the client's career is not in line with purpose both employability and satisfaction may not be obtained. According to Fugate et al., (2004), employability is work specific active adaptability that enables workers to identify and realize career opportunities. On the other hands, employability is a set of skills, understandings and personal attributes that make graduates more likely to gain employment (Jollands, 2015). Bertson et al. (2008) however, argues that employability refers to an individual's perception of his or her possibilities of getting new, equal, or better employment. In this study, it is assumed that the individuals' possibilities of getting satisfactory jobs can be enhanced by their sense of purpose. Accordingly, Oliver (2015) emphasized that employability has more to do with being employable, irrespective of the prevailing economic situations, and this study presupposes that linking purpose to career support that. The author added that employability entails the graduates being able to discern, gain, adapt and develop various skills, understandings and personal attributes that make them more likely to find and create meaningful work that benefits themselves, the employer, the society and the economy.

Paadi (2014) observed that employability denotes a graduate's capacity and willingness to become and remain attractive in the labour market. The author further argued that employability is the ability of graduates to secure jobs in the labour market, being equipped with the skills most envisaged by the

employer and the ability to take part and contribute to the knowledge economy by applying what they learned in higher education and also improve their social standing and the country's economy. From this point of view, employability involves being capable of getting, creating and keeping fulfilling work; and having the knowledge, understanding, skills, experience and personal attributes to move self within the labour market in as much as the specific duty in the labour market is not derailing from the perceived purpose of the individuals. This may also mean that having a set of skills, knowledge, understanding and personal attributes that make a person more likely to choose and secure occupations in which they can be satisfied and successful is enhanced by their sense of purpose (Römgens et al., 2020). Following a career based on purpose may lead to a series of discoveries of self and environment that may increase the likelihood of finding a job for the individual. In addition, purpose-based career coaching enhances the acquisition of employability skills through empowerment and development processes. People with a purpose-based career, for instance, discover and develop talents, skills, and potential that make them employable. It is unclear, however, how childhood education teachers and counsellors who have struggled to help young people make career decisions would view the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing graduates' employability skills.

1.3. Statement of Problem

It is unfortunate that among most individuals, career exploration activities do not typically cultivate their ability to have a sense of purpose and meaning in life, despite its importance for overall life satisfaction and career satisfaction (Kosine et al., 2008). This might be due to poor perception of significance of purpose-based career decision-making. On this note, young people are still vulnerable to wrong career choice and this has amounted to a low level of employability and a high level of unemployment, underemployment, low productivity, dissatisfaction, and failures in purpose fulfillment. When people feel their careers have a sense of purpose their lives become more meaningful, and they may be willing to learn more skills that will make them employable. Supporting this, scholars believe that those who treat their work as a source of meaning are considered to be more effective at employability skills such as teamwork, networking, problem-solving, commitment and computing to enhance their work, and to obtain a higher level of job satisfaction (Kosine et al., 2008; Steger & Dik, 2010). The challenge of graduates' employability becomes severe when graduates career pursuit is not based on purpose. Moreover, the perception of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching framework as strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria remains unknown. Hence, the need for this study.

1.4. Purpose of the Study

The objectives of this study are to investigate:

- (a) The general knowledge level of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria.
- (b) The perception of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates in Nigeria.
- (c) Teachers' and counsellors' perception of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria.
- (d) Teachers' and counsellors' perception of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models.

1.5. Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- (a) What are the general knowledge levels of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates?
- (b) What are the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates?
- (c) What are the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates?
- (d) What are the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models?

1.6. Hypothesis

Four null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. They are:

- (a) The general knowledge level of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates does not differ significantly based on gender.
- (b) There is no significant gender difference in the perception of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates.
- (c) There is no significant gender difference in teachers' and counsellors' perception of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates.
- (d) There is no significant gender difference in teachers' and counsellors' perception of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study adopted a survey research design. Prior to the survey, desk research was conducted for 2021-2022 to generate deep knowledge of career theories. Google Scholar, Scopus and DOAJ databases were used to retrieve career theories and models in journal articles that published studies on career-related concepts. Following the limitations, and challenges provided in the previous studies for making the right career choice and fulfilling destiny, the researchers were able to generate basic concepts, beliefs, goals, and techniques covering purpose-based career coaching.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

This study observed the ethical procedures set by American Psychology Association. The research received ethical clearance from the Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka. All the participants signed informed consent form before commencement of the study.

2.2. Area of the Study

This study was conducted in South-East religions of Nigeria. This covers Enugu, Anambra, Imo, Abia and Ebonyi States.

2.3. Population and Sample

The participants of the study were 100 secondary school teachers and 100 school counsellors

from South-East region of Nigeria. The teachers and counsellors were permanent staff in government schools in South-Eastern region of Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure, which comprised of purposive, simple random, and stratified sampling techniques was adopted in this study.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection

This study used a survey questionnaire titled "Purpose-based Career Coaching and Employability Questionnaire" (PCCEQ) to collect data. There are four clusters in the instrument, and there are 20 items in cluster 1, 11 items in cluster 2, 10 items in cluster 3, and 10 items in cluster 4. In the first cluster, respondents are assessed on their knowledge of purpose-based career coaching. Those items in the second cluster measure their applicability in Nigerian settings. Also, the third cluster had items measuring the workability of purpose-based career coaching in different school settings. Lastly, the fourth cluster compares purpose-based career coaching with other career models. The items on the questionnaire were written after thorough research into purpose-based career coaching literature. Four experts in psychometrics, measurement and evaluation, career counselling and educational psychology reviewed the instrument after it was written. Each expert had a doctorate degree in their field of expertise, and was a professor by rank in their academic field. After both researchers and validators considered and agreed upon all corrections and criticisms, the final draft of the instrument was produced. A trial test of the instrument was conducted with 15 secondary school teachers and 15 secondary school counsellors in the South-South part of Nigeria, near the study area. According to the trial tested data collected and analyzed, the instrument's internal consistency coefficient was 0.854 Alpha in the overall, whereas it was 0.799 for cluster 1, 0.891 for cluster 2, 0.844 for cluster 3, and 0.882 for cluster 4.

2.5. Data Collection Technique and Study Procedure

The researchers and research assistants visited selected schools in the study area to mobilize the participants for the study. A month before the start of the study, all participants were recruited and made to attend a 3-day sensitivity workshop. During the 3-day sensitivity workshop, participants were exposed to the major concepts, tenets, principles, applicability and potentials of purpose-based career coaching model in order to form impressions and perceptions. In the workshop, there were three sessions every day, anchored by researchers and assisted by five research assistants. Two international consultants and three career counselling consultants at three top Nigerian universities verified and approved the workshop materials and contents. Moreover, the criteria for using workshop in a research scenario were followed as discussed in scholastic manuscripts (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017). In the day 1 of the workshop, after registration and preliminary assessment and formalities, the participants were taught the concept, history, principles and importance of purpose-based career coaching in employability skills acquisition and development. In the day two, the focus of the workshop was on the key techniques used in purpose-based career coaching such as reimagining, spiritualizing, self-discovery, identification, matching and engagement. Further on the third day, the workshop featured the relationship between purpose-based career and employability skills acquisition, and development, as well as how the understanding of purpose may be used as a motivation for employability skills acquisition and development.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The method used in analyzing the data include percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test and bar charts.

3. Results and Discussion

The result of this long-term research is presented as purpose-based career coaching: an emerging coaching framework. Emphases are placed on the goals, beliefs, techniques and career categorizations.

Table 1: Participants' Characteristics

Categories	Number	Gender		Workplace		Age
		Males	Females	Government secondary school	Government secondary school	
Teachers	100	38	62	100	-	31 years old
Counsellors	100	44	56	-	100	30 years old

This study involved 100 teachers and 100 counsellors, totaling 200 participants. The average age of teachers was 30 years old, while the average age of counsellors was 31 years old. Out of 200 participants, 62 were female teachers and 38 were male teachers. The average age of counselors was 42, while 58 were female. In addition to providing a glimpse into the gender distribution and average age of the teachers and counselors included in this study, these statistics also provide an overview of the demographics of the participants as shown in Table 1.

Table 2: Participants' gender analysis

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Participants * Gender	Between Groups	(Combined)	.083	1	.083	.331	.566
	Within Groups		49.917	198	.252		
	Total		50.000	199			

Table 2 specifies that there was no significant difference between the male and female participants, $F(1,198)=0.331$, $P=.566$.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics showing pre-workshop knowledge levels of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates.

	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Knowledge Level
I am not aware of purpose-based career coaching	3.30	.69	Low
I don't know whether purpose-based career coaching can increase the employability of graduates	3.40	.68	Low
I have participated in purpose-based seminars or workshops before	1.57	.81	Low
Purpose-based career coaching was not part of my course content in school	3.65	.86	Low
I never heard of a career model that links one's divine purpose to career pursuit	2.53	.69	Moderate
I didn't know that there is any career that defines and reveals the essence of one's existence	2.56	.64	Moderate
I didn't know I can fulfill my purpose through my career	2.03	.84	Low
I don't know whether I can use career as platform for purpose pursuit	3.66	.85	Low
It is strange to know that purpose is connected strongly to one's career	3.33	.68	Low
I don't know anything about purpose	3.33	.64	Low
I don't know how to discover my purpose	3.5	.84	Low
I don't know how to guide my client/students to discover purpose	3.66	.85	Low
It is surprising to know that every career has purpose	3.28	.68	Low
I am not surprise to know that every individual has purpose	1.30	.64	Low
I know the best career is the one that is connected to one's purpose	1.52	.86	Low
I would like to pursue the career that will enhance my purpose fulfillment	3.63	.88	Low
I don't know how to help my clients/students define the reason for their existence, and choose career accordingly	3.22	.67	Low
Some of my clients/students want to know the will of God in their careers but I don't know how to help them	3.30	.64	Low
I am lacking knowledge about the career that gives one sense of life meaning	3.53	.86	Low
It is unfortunate that I don't know how to link my clients'/students' careers to their purpose	3.66	.85	low

As presented in Table 3, the teachers and counselors were assessed regarding their knowledge of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing the employability of graduates. It was found

that teachers and counselors were not knowledgeable about purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing graduates' employability. As a result of their low knowledge levels at the pre-workshop assessment, the teachers and counselors scored high on most negative items, but low on most positive items.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics showing post-workshop knowledge levels of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates .

	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Knowledge Level
I am not aware of purpose-based career coaching	1.30	.22	High
I don't know whether purpose-based career coaching can increase the employability of graduates	1.20	.45	High
I have participated in purpose-based seminars or workshops before	1.57	.44	High
Purpose-based career coaching was not part of my course content in school	3.65	.55	Low
I never heard of a career model that links one's divine purpose to career pursuit	1.43	.66	High
I didn't know that there is any career that defines and reveals the essence of one's existence	1.46	.78	High
I didn't know I can fulfill my purpose through my career	1.03	.99	High
I don't know whether I can use career as platform for purpose pursuit	1.46	.20	High
It is strange to know that purpose is connected strongly to one's career	1.33	.22	High
I don't know anything about purpose	1.23	.34	High
I don't know how to discover my purpose	1.25	.56	High
I don't know how to guide my client/students to discover purpose	1.46	.77	High
It is surprising to know that every career has purpose	1.38	.66	High
I am not surprise to know that every individual has purpose	3.80	.33	High
I know the best career is the one that is connected to one's purpose	3.52	.76	High
I would like to pursue the career that will enhance my purpose fulfillment	3.83	.89	High
I don't know how to help my clients/students define the reason for their existence, and choose career accordingly	1.12	.58	High
Some of my clients/students want to know the will of God in their careers but I don't know how to help them	1.10	.89	High
I am lacking knowledge about the career that gives one sense of life meaning	1.73	.56	High

It is unfortunate that I don't know how to link my clients'/students' careers to their purpose 1.76 .55 High

Table 4 shows that the knowledge level of the teachers and counsellors increased through the workshop with respect to the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates. Considering purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing the employability of graduates, there has been a significant increase in the knowledge level of teachers and counselors. Before the commencement of the study, participants did not have much knowledge about this coaching approach. But after the workshop, they have developed significantly in their knowledge. It is clear from this that the workshop was effective in equipping teachers and counselors with the information and tools they need to implement purpose-based career coaching effectively.

Table 5: ANOVA showing the differences between teachers and counsellors in terms of their perceived general knowledge of the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates.

			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I am not aware of purpose-based career coaching previously	Between Groups	(Combined)	2.000	1	2.000	4.304	.039
	Within Groups		92.000	198	.465		
	Total		94.000	199			
I don't know whether purpose-based career coaching can increase the employability of graduates	Between Groups	(Combined)	2.000	1	2.000	4.400	.037
	Within Groups		90.000	198	.455		
	Total		92.000	199			
I have participated in purpose-based seminars or workshops before	Between Groups	(Combined)	.845	1	.845	1.284	.259
	Within Groups		130.310	198	.658		
	Total		131.155	199			
Purpose-based career coaching was not part of my course content in school	Between Groups	(Combined)	.405	1	.405	.544	.462
	Within Groups		147.390	198	.744		
	Total		147.795	199			
I never heard of a career model that links one's divine purpose to career pursuit	Between Groups	(Combined)	3.125	1	3.125	6.671	.011
	Within Groups		92.750	198	.468		
	Total		95.875	199			
I didn't know that there is any career that defines and reveals the essence of one's existence	Between Groups	(Combined)	.720	1	.720	1.752	.187
	Within Groups		81.360	198	.411		
	Total		82.080	199			
I didn't know I can fulfill my purpose through my career	Between Groups	(Combined)	.845	1	.845	1.192	.276
	Within Groups		140.310	198	.709		
	Total		141.155	199			

I don't know whether I can use career as platform for purpose pursuit	Between Groups	(Combined)	.605	1	.605	.828	.364
	Within Groups		144.590	198	.730		
	Total		145.195	199			
It is strange to know that purpose is connected strongly to one's career	Between Groups	(Combined)	.005	1	.005	.011	.917
	Within Groups		91.870	198	.464		
	Total		91.875	199			
I don't know anything about purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.434	.511
	Within Groups		82.040	198	.414		
	Total		82.220	199			
I don't know how to discover my purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	.405	1	.405	.568	.452
	Within Groups		141.190	198	.713		
	Total		141.595	199			
I don't know how to guide my client/students to discover purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	.605	1	.605	.828	.364
	Within Groups		144.590	198	.730		
	Total		145.195	199			
It is surprising to know that every career has purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	1.445	1	1.445	3.133	.078
	Within Groups		91.310	198	.461		
	Total		92.755	199			
I am not surprise to know that every individual has purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		
	Total		82.000	199			
I know the best career is the one that is connected to one's purpose	Between Groups	(Combined)	.080	1	.080	.109	.742
	Within Groups		145.840	198	.737		
	Total		145.920	199			
I would like to pursue the career that will enhance my purpose fulfillment	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.231	.631
	Within Groups		154.440	198	.780		
	Total		154.620	199			
I don't know how to help my clients/students define the reason for their existence, and choose career accordingly	Between Groups	(Combined)	.080	1	.080	.176	.676
	Within Groups		90.240	198	.456		
	Total		90.320	199			
Some of my clients/students want to know the will of God in their careers but I don't	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		

know how to help them	Total		82.000	199			
I am lacking knowledge about the career that gives one sense of life meaning	Between Groups (Combined)		.245	1	.245	.333	.564
	Within Groups		145.510	198	.735		
	Total		145.755	199			
It is unfortunate that I don't know how to link my clients'/students' careers to their purpose	Between Groups (Combined)		.605	1	.605	.828	.364
	Within Groups		144.590	198	.730		
	Total		145.195	199			

Table 5 shows that general knowledge level of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates only differ significantly in three items. First, in terms of being aware of purpose-based career coaching previously; second knowing whether purpose-based career coaching can increase the employability of graduates; and third, previous knowledge of a career model that links one's divine purpose to career pursuit.

Figure 1: Bar chart showing general knowledge levels of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates

Figure 1 is a bar chart showing the general knowledge level (in percentage) of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates. From the chart, counsellors had higher percentage than the childhood teachers.

Table 6: Descriptive statistics showing the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Purpose-based career coaching helps to increase self-discovery, thereby enhances employability of graduates	199	3.30	.68	-.461	.172
Purpose-based career coaching exposes graduates to their talents which can make them employable	200	3.30	.64	.783	.172
Purpose-based career coaching exposes graduates to their long-lasting passions which can make them employable	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172
Purpose-based career coaching enhances acquisition of graduates' employability skills	200	3.65	.86	-1.528	.172
Purpose-based career coaching promotes self-reliance among graduates	200	3.23	.67	-.306	.172
Purpose-based career coaching ensures self-fulfillment thereby encourages graduates to take up tasks that make them fulfilled	200	3.30	.64	.783	.172
Purpose-based career coaching makes occupational decision-making easy, thereby increases graduates' employability	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172
Purpose-based career coaching enhances acquisition of graduates' employability skills	200	3.65	.86	-1.528	.172
Purpose-based career coaching improves entrepreneurial mindset	200	3.27	.68	-.391	.172
Purpose-based career coaching helps one to fulfill career without jeopardizing one's divine mandate	200	3.30	.64	.783	.172
Purpose-based career coaching meets clients' career needs and interests without jeopardizing their divine mandates	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172

Table 6 shows that the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates is high. This means that they viewed purpose-based career coaching as having high applicability in Nigeria.

Table 7: ANOVA showing the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purpose-based career coaching helps to increase self-discovery, thereby enhances employability of graduates	Between Groups	(Combined)	1.950	1	1.950	4.270	.040
	Within Groups		89.960	197	.457		
	Total		91.910	198			
Purpose-based career coaching exposes graduates to their talents which can make them employable	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		
	Total		82.000	199			
Purpose-based career coaching exposes graduates to their long-lasting passions which can make them employable	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups		143.640	198	.725		
	Total		143.820	199			
Purpose-based career coaching enhances acquisition of graduates' employability skills	Between Groups	(Combined)	.405	1	.405	.544	.462
	Within Groups		147.390	198	.744		
	Total		147.795	199			
Purpose-based career coaching promotes self-reliance among graduates	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.399	.528
	Within Groups		89.240	198	.451		
	Total		89.420	199			
Purpose-based career coaching ensures self-fulfilment thereby encourages graduates to take up tasks that make them fulfilled	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		
	Total		82.000	199			
Purpose-based career coaching makes occupational decision-making easy, thereby increases graduates' employability	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups		143.640	198	.725		
	Total		143.820	199			
Purpose-based career coaching enhances acquisition of graduates' employability skills	Between Groups	(Combined)	.405	1	.405	.544	.462
	Within Groups		147.390	198	.744		
	Total		147.795	199			
Purpose-based career coaching improves entrepreneurial mindset	Between Groups	(Combined)	.845	1	.845	1.816	.179
	Within Groups		92.110	198	.465		
	Total		92.955	199			
Purpose-based career coaching helps one to fulfill career without jeopardizing one's divine	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		

mandate	Total	82.000	199			
Purpose-based career coaching meets clients' career needs and interests without jeopardizing their divine mandates	Between (Combined) Groups	.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups	143.640	198	.725		
	Total	143.820	199			

Table 7 shows that the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates only differ significantly in one item which states that purpose-based career coaching helps to increase self-discovery, thereby enhances employability of graduates.

Figure 2: A bar chart showing the shows that the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability

Figure 2 is a bar chart showing the shows that the perceptions of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates. From the chart, counsellors had higher percentage than the teachers.

Table 8: Showing the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian primary schools	200	3.67	.85	-1.630	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian secondary schools	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian tertiary institutions	200	3.65	.86	-1.528	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is easy to handle by Nigerians	200	3.23	.67	-.306	.172
Purpose-based career coaching does not require too much technicalities	200	3.30	.64	.783	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be used by trained non-career counsellors	200	3.54	.84	-.279	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian primary schools	200	3.66	.84	-1.538	.172
Purpose-based career coaching does not require too much laboratory equipment	200	3.54	.84	-.279	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out through virtual means	200	3.66	.84	-1.538	.172
Purpose-based career coaching can be conducted on both one-to-one and group based	200	3.44	2.96	13.071	.172

Table 8 shows that the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates. Both the teachers and the counsellors were of opinion that purpose-based career coaching has high workability.

Table 9: The teachers’ and counsellors’ perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates

				Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian primary schools	Between Groups	(Combined)		.980	1	.980	1.374	.243
	Within Groups			141.240	198	.713		
	Total			142.220	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian secondary schools	Between Groups	(Combined)		.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups			143.640	198	.725		
	Total			143.820	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian tertiary institutions	Between Groups	(Combined)		.405	1	.405	.544	.462
	Within Groups			147.390	198	.744		
	Total			147.795	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is easy to handle by Nigerians	Between Groups	(Combined)		.180	1	.180	.399	.528
	Within Groups			89.240	198	.451		
	Total			89.420	199			
Purpose-based career coaching does not require too much technicalities	Between Groups	(Combined)		.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups			82.000	198	.414		
	Total			82.000	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be used by trained non-career counsellors	Between Groups	(Combined)		.320	1	.320	.448	.504
	Within Groups			141.360	198	.714		
	Total			141.680	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out in Nigerian primary schools	Between Groups	(Combined)		.720	1	.720	1.017	.314
	Within Groups			140.160	198	.708		
	Total			140.880	199			
Purpose-based career coaching does not require too much laboratory equipment	Between Groups	(Combined)		.320	1	.320	.448	.504
	Within Groups			141.360	198	.714		
	Total			141.680	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be carried out through virtual means	Between Groups	(Combined)		.720	1	.720	1.017	.314
	Within Groups			140.160	198	.708		
	Total			140.880	199			
Purpose-based career coaching can be conducted on both one-to-one and group based	Between Groups	(Combined)		11.520	1	11.520	1.319	.252
	Within Groups			1729.760	198	8.736		
	Total			1741.280	199			

Table 9 shows no significant difference in the teachers’ and counsellors’ perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates.

Figure 3: A bar chart of teachers’ and counsellors’ perceptions of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates

Table 10: Showing the teachers’ and counsellors’ perceptions of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models

	N	Mean	Std.	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Deviation	Statistic	Std.
			Statistic	Statistic	Error
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than John Holland’s Typology	200	3.41	.64	.398	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Ann Roe’s career theory	200	3.54	.84	-.279	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Pearson’s career theory	200	3.66	.84	-1.538	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Super’s career theory	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Ginzberg’s theory	200	3.66	.84	-1.538	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Tiedeman’s career theory	200	3.53	.85	-.268	.172

Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Krumboltz's career theory	200	3.67	.83	-1.578	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Hoppock's career theory	200	3.24	.67	-.316	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than	200	3.30	.64	.783	.172
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than any other theory I have learnt	200	3.52	.86	-.257	.172

Regarding effectiveness, table 10 shows that the teachers and counsellors perceived purpose-based career coaching to be effective when compared to foreign career theories they have used previously.

Table 11: Showing the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models

				Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than John Holland's Typology	Between Groups	(Combined)		2.420	1	2.420	5.992	.015
	Within Groups			79.960	198	.404		
	Total			82.380	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Ann Roe's career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)		.320	1	.320	.448	.504
	Within Groups			141.360	198	.714		
	Total			141.680	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Pearson's career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)		.720	1	.720	1.017	.314
	Within Groups			140.160	198	.708		
	Total			140.880	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Super's career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)		.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups			143.640	198	.725		
	Total			143.820	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Ginzberg's theory	Between Groups	(Combined)		.720	1	.720	1.017	.314
	Within Groups			140.160	198	.708		
	Total			140.880	199			

Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Tiedeman's career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)	.180	1	.180	.248	.619
	Within Groups		143.640	198	.725		
	Total		143.820	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Krumboltz' career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)	.980	1	.980	1.414	.236
	Within Groups		137.240	198	.693		
	Total		138.220	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than Hoppock's career theory	Between Groups	(Combined)	.320	1	.320	.719	.398
	Within Groups		88.160	198	.445		
	Total		88.480	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than	Between Groups	(Combined)	.000	1	.000	.000	1.000
	Within Groups		82.000	198	.414		
	Total		82.000	199			
Purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than any other theory I have learnt	Between Groups	(Combined)	.080	1	.080	.109	.742
	Within Groups		145.840	198	.737		
	Total		145.920	199			

Table 11 shows no significant difference in the teachers' and counsellors' perceptions of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models, except in number one item. They differ in the opinion that purpose-based career coaching is more detailed and effective in Nigeria than John Holland's Typology.

Figure 4: A bar chart of teachers’ and counsellors’ perceptions of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, when compared to other known career models

Four null hypotheses formulated in this study were tested at 0.05 level of significance, as presented on table 12.

Table 12: Summary of multivariate analysis to determine gender differences in the perceptions on purpose-based career coaching

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	Knowledge level	3.231 ^a	1	3.231	.047	.828
	Applicability	8.049 ^b	1	8.049	.398	.529
	Workability	6.712 ^c	1	6.712	.207	.650
	Effectiveness	.372 ^d	1	.372	.013	.909
Intercept	Knowledge level	912500.959	1	912500.959	13397.646	.000
	Applicability	269348.049	1	269348.049	13328.581	.000
	Workability	237606.994	1	237606.994	7312.415	.000
	Effectiveness	234835.065	1	234835.065	8226.922	.000
Gender	Knowledge level	3.231	1	3.231	.047	.828
	Applicability	8.049	1	8.049	.398	.529
	Workability	6.712	1	6.712	.207	.650
	Effectiveness	.372	1	.372	.013	.909
Error	Knowledge level	13417.483	197	68.109		
	Applicability	3981.036	197	20.208		
	Workability	6401.247	197	32.494		
	Effectiveness	5623.307	197	28.545		
Total	Knowledge level	963069.000	199			
	Applicability	284696.000	199			
	Workability	252991.000	199			
	Effectiveness	249959.000	199			
Corrected Total	Knowledge level	13420.714	198			
	Applicability	3989.085	198			
	Workability	6407.960	198			
	Effectiveness	5623.678	198			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = -.005)

b. R Squared = .002 (Adjusted R Squared = -.003)

c. R Squared = .001 (Adjusted R Squared = -.004)

d. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = -.005)

Table 12 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of F (0.047) for gender difference in the general knowledge level of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates is 0.828. Since the probability value of 0.828 is greater than the .05 level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that the general knowledge level of teachers and counsellors regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates does differ significantly based on gender. Table 11 shows that the probability associated with the calculated

value of $F (.398)$ for gender difference in the perception of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates is $.529$. Since the probability value of $.529$ is greater than the $.05$ level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that the perception of teachers and counsellors with respect to applicability of purpose-based career coaching to increase employability of graduates does differ significantly based on gender.

In terms of workability, Table 12 shows that the probability associated with the calculated value of $F (.207)$ is $.650$. Since the probability value of $.650$ is greater than the $.05$ level of significance ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there is no significant gender difference in teachers' and counsellors' perception of the workability of purpose-based career coaching as strategy for increasing employability of graduates. Finally, results presented in Table 11 shows that there is no significant gender difference in teachers' and counsellors' perception of the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates, given that $F (0.13)$ is $.909$, at 0.05 level of significance. The knowledge level of the teachers and counsellors increased through the workshop with respect the use of purpose-based career coaching as a strategy for increasing employability of graduates. Before the workshop, the teachers and the counsellors, through interview, acknowledged that they did not have adequate knowledge regarding the use of purpose-based career coaching. The workshop sensitized and exposed them to the concept, principles, techniques, and usage of purpose-based career coaching, especially in a Nigerian setting. This agrees with previous findings that workshop can be effective tool for research (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017).

After attending workshops on purpose-based career coaching, and reading career theories and models manuscripts, the teachers and counsellors perceived purpose-based career coaching to be applicable, workable and effective strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria. As was noted in the workshops when the graduates are able to link their careers to their purpose it makes it easier for them to acquire skills that will enhance the fulfillment the purpose. Thus, teachers, counsellors or career coaches are meant to apply purpose-based career coaching in every situation. This finding does not support Zunker's (2011) notion that no single theory is suitable for all situations or for every individual. The teachers and counsellors perceived purpose-based coaching to be applicable in every situation to help client make career decisions, explorations and development. This assertion could be due to the fact that purpose is the central point of life, and whoever finds purpose would find meaning, and makes decision and adjustment easily (Kosine et al., 2008). However, the teachers and counsellors differ significantly in the statement that purpose-based career coaching helps to increase self-discovery, thereby enhances employability of graduates. The difference could be due to the fact that counsellors may have had previous experience with various career coaching models than childhood education teachers due to the nature of their training and practice. This notwithstanding, the workshop exposed both the counsellors and teachers to the same level of knowledge, thereby creating a balance in their perception. In addition, all the hypothesis formulated in this study were not rejected, implying that gender did not have any significant contribution or influence on the participants' perception. This finding does not support gender-career bias indicated in previous studies (Kramer et al., 2021). The major influence in career decision should be individual's purpose, not gender.

In addition to increasing the employability of graduates, purpose-based career coaching has important societal implications as well. Choosing a career that aligns with your purpose increases the likelihood of finding meaningful and fulfilling employment, which enhances your employability as you possess the skills and qualities employers prefer. As a result of purpose-based career coaching,

graduates are more likely to find careers aligned with their personal values and interests, which in turn reduces turnover rates and enhances productivity. A purpose-based approach encourages graduates to discover their purpose and grow personally. By identifying their purpose, graduates will develop a strong sense of identity and direction, resulting in increased self-confidence and resilience. Graduating with a clear purpose contributes to the well-being of society by contributing to their communities, engaging in meaningful work, and contributing to the overall well-being of the community. The effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching may be limited by some limitations, despite its great potential. A purpose-based career coaching program may require additional resources, such as career counsellors and training programmes, but the long-term benefits, such as increased employability and lower turnover rates, may outweigh the initial costs. Some individuals may resist the purpose-based approach, preferring a more traditional career trajectory instead. Career coaching programmes that support this can help shape a more purposeful and resilient workforce, but it is increasingly important for people to find meaning and purpose in their work. Cultures and individuals can have different purposes and values. To provide graduates with customized guidance and support based on their cultural backgrounds and values, career coaching programs should acknowledge and respect these differences. To enhance graduates' employability, more research is needed on purpose-based career coaching. It would be helpful to conduct longitudinal studies to assess if purpose-based career coaching would increase graduates' employability, job satisfaction, and overall life satisfaction over the long-term. The effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching should be compared with traditional career counseling methods, such as personality and skills tests. Taking into account the unique values and aspirations of each cultural group should be considered in further research regarding purpose-based career coaching. The effectiveness of virtual career coaching programs should be examined more closely than face-to-face career coaching programs, given the increasing use of online platforms. In order to refine and improve the effectiveness of purpose-based career coaching programs, continuous feedback and improvement should be sought from graduates and career coaches. In addressing these limitations and conducting further research, we can better understand how purpose-based career coaching impacts graduates' employability and develop more effective strategies for helping them thrive in their career paths.

4. Conclusion

The conclusion reached in this study is that teachers and counsellors perceived purpose-based career coaching as effective, applicable and workable strategy for increasing employability of graduates in Nigeria. This coaching model has numerous advantages over existing career models and theories since it helps clients to discover their purpose and the suitable career, thereby enhancing employability skills acquisition and development. Each individual's peculiarities and uniqueness are also taken into consideration in relation to career choice, development, adaptability, and progress. Thus, purpose-based career coaching benefits individuals, organizations, institutions, and nations because it provides meaning, motivation, and focus to people, thereby generating purpose-driven individuals, organizations, institutions and nations. Also, purpose-based career coaching success lies in its ability to reach diverse communities with cross-cultural perspectives, as well as to take into account minority groups, abandoned tribes, adolescents, indigenous peoples, disabled people, displaced people, people of diverse ethnicities and belief systems. It is recommended that University and college career counselling services should be enhanced so that graduates receive personalized guidance and support. To ensure graduates are well-prepared to navigate the job market and make informed decisions about

their future career paths, purpose-based career coaching should be included in these services. Also, graduates should be evaluated based on their values, interests, and strengths that are connected with their purpose. In order to increase job satisfaction and engagement, career coaches can help graduates align their career choices with their personal values.

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Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

MSO and MFO conceived and designed the research. MSO, MFO, ZA developed the research design, instrument, supervised the collection and analysis of data.

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The datasets generated and/or analyzed in this article can be obtained from the corresponding author on reasonable request. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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